

Location

Teknikhöjden, Stockholm - Sweden

Innovation

1.4 BIM for circular value flow planning

Partners

Demo Consultants

Mainflux

Saint Gobain (outside Reincarnate)

DATA TYPES, TOOLS, REPOSITORIES, URLS

Data types

Weight

Customer information

Order number

Tools

Glass buddy

Repositories or platforms

Resulte

Mainflux

EPR system

CRM system

SUMMARY OF SCOPE AND GOALS

This demonstration focuses on illustrating a circular value flow where flat glass from existing buildings is recovered, processed, and used to produce new flat glass, ultimately reinstalled as a window component. The aim is to show how both the physical movement of materials and the flow of information are essential for enabling circularity.

A key aspect of circular physical flows is the timely exchange of accurate data. Each actor in the value chain must be able to share and access relevant information at the right moment. In this context, the demonstration highlights how material can be traced both physically and digitally across different steps in the value chain.

The demonstration also shows how Circular Value Flow Planning (CVFP), along with the required digital capabilities, is integrated into the CP-IM platform. This includes using data for circularity assessments and strategic material planning

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

METHOD	Glass – Recyclable (kg)	Glass – Downgrade (kg)	Est. CO2 savings (kg)	Accuracy % (Recyclable)
Initial guess	3105	N/A	1646	89%
Manual inventory	3887	22	2060	112%
3D scan	4096	22	2171	118%
3D & LiDAR	5148	22	2728	148%
Process output	3481	285	1844	100%

IMAGES

*Glass cullet
ready for delivery
to Saint-Gobain*

IMPACT

MEDIUM

Techno-Economic
Impact

MEDIUM-HIGH

Societal Impact

MEDIUM

Scientific Impact

CONTACTS

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